

Policy measures to develop a favourable regulatory/market framework

FRESH-D7.5- Policy measures to develop a favourable regulatory/market framework

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Abbreviations:

EU - European Union

PF – Potassium Formate

FRESH - Formate for Renewable Energy Storage (GA 101069605)

COP21- 21st Conference of the Parties on climate

SET - European Strategic Energy Technology

IPCEI - Important Project of Common European Interest

CCU - Carbon Capture and Utilization

RED - Renewable Energy Directive

KET - Key Enabling Technologies

JRC - Joint Research Center

Power-to-X - Technologies that convert electricity into fuels or chemicals

SES Smart Energy Systems - European Commission's in-house science service, informs EU policy-making via independent research on more secure, inclusive, smarter and interoperable electricity systems.

1. Executive summary

The FRESH project falls under the Horizon Europe “Climate, Energy and Mobility” domain. Within this context, the objectives of FRESH are clearly aligned with enabling *renewable energy storage solutions*, which require a supportive regulatory and market framework. To this end, FRESH partners have developed this report with recommendations towards policymakers (Member States and EU via the European Parliament). Challenges and obstacles of existing legislation are identified and policy recommendations to policymakers are presented. Energy storage is essential to achieving the EU clean energy transition and clean energy security goals. While the Electricity Directive (EU) 2019/944 and Electricity Regulation (EU) 2019/943 provide a clear framework for storage integration, deployment across member states remains uneven. Germany, Spain, France, and Italy have made significant progress through market reform and national incentives, yet regulatory barriers and fragmented funding continue to limit large-scale development.

This report outlines current EU and national measures promoting energy storage and provides policy recommendations to strengthen EU-wide deployment, enhance system flexibility, and support a sustainable, competitive energy market. These aspects will strengthen the application of new storage technologies such as the FRESH technology.

2. Introduction and FRESH project background

In 2015, 195 countries reached an agreement at COP21 to limit global warming to well below 2 °C. This agreement entered into force in 2020 and to achieve its ambitious goals, radical emission reductions will be required. In line with this, the EU has set ambitious goals to meet its climate and energy targets in the 2020 Climate and Energy Package. The greenhouse gas reduction targets of the EU are also reflected in the European Strategic Energy Technology (SET) Plan, which aims to accelerate the development and deployment of low carbon technologies. The developments in FRESH have demonstrated feasible technology for using CO₂ utilization for energy storage to help not only in reducing CO₂ emissions but also help the energy resilience of the EU. Efficient energy storage is a fundamental pillar of the transition to renewable energy (Figure 1). FRESH also aligns with the EU Bio-economy Strategy for new approaches to ensure that fossil fuels are replaced with sustainable alternatives as part of the shift to a post-petroleum society ambition and with the Circular Economy package for a green and resource-efficient Europe. Much more than the renewable (biomass) resources considered in the bio-based economy, CO₂ is indeed the ultimate sustainable resource for a wide range of chemicals and polymers. It does not pose problems with direct or indirect land-use changes, has no or low impact on food, land, water or biodiversity and does not present a risk of feedstock competition. The CCU developments envisaged in FRESH contribute to this ambition by considering CO₂ as an essential part of short and closed carbon cycles. Advanced materials are one of the most strategically relevant Key Enabling Technologies (KETs) in the EU. The core of the FRESH activities (Figure 2) encompasses renewable electricity integration, the development and application of two conversion platforms (CO₂ to PF and PF to electricity) via innovative electrosynthesis processes, which are highly relevant for gas conversion processes in general. Cross-cutting KET aspects concern the integration with Nanotechnology (development of nanoparticles in the catalytic processes for anode and cathode) as well as with Sustainable Process Industries (SPIRE) (energy efficiency, process industry more resource- and energy-efficient, green products). The science and technology innovations in FRESH also fit with the vision that eco-innovation and green technologies are key to Europe’s future. The Eco-Innovation Action Plan specifically stresses the importance

of innovative SMEs to turn environmental challenges into business opportunities. This is recognized by and reflected in the FRESH consortium, with the involvement of 3 innovative SMEs.

Figure 1: Schematic of operation and use of renewable energy storage system based upon batteries (source www.totalenergies.com).

Figure 2: FRESH technology energy storage cycle based upon potassium formate (PF) as energy vector.

The world energy outlook 2024 Energy storage is identified as a critical enabler for integrating higher shares of renewables and strengthening energy security. The following aspects were identified:

- Policy support for energy storage is expanding globally, with major international commitments to increasing installed capacity.
- The G7 has agreed to contribute to a global target of 1,500 GW of installed energy storage capacity by 2030, representing a sixfold increase from 2023 levels.
- Battery storage is expected to provide the majority of this expansion, outpacing other forms such as pumped hydro.
- Installed battery storage capacity is projected to rise from nearly 90 GW in 2023 to 850 GW in 2030.
- The average duration of battery storage is expected to increase from around two hours currently to three hours by 2030.
- By 2035, battery storage is projected to be second only to natural gas as a source of dispatchable capacity, with a 16-fold increase in capacity compared to today.
- Battery storage complements solar PV effectively, supporting grid flexibility and reliability.
- Both behind-the-meter and utility-scale battery storage applications are expected to see significant growth.
- Short-term flexibility in power systems is increasing four times faster than electricity demand from 2023 to 2035.
- New sources of flexibility, led by battery storage and demand-response measures, are emerging as the role of coal diminishes rapidly.
- The expansion of energy storage is essential for meeting the target to triple renewables capacity by 2030 (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Share of renewable electricity generation by technology, 2000-2030 (source IEA website).

3. Objectives of this report

Promotion of renewable energy production and storage requires strategic decisions and their step-by-step implementation, including ensuring a high quality of public governance, political participation of citizens, economic deregulation and business freedom, educational reforms, etc. To increase the positive impact on the environment, these actions should be accompanied by economic decarbonization strategies (effective system of CO₂ emissions monitoring, green infrastructure development, smart industry formation, etc.).¹ The objectives of this study were to examine the existing EU regulatory and market framework in the context of the FRESH project. The key application of the FRESH project is the renewable energy *storage* sector and consequently the emphasis is on examining how such frameworks can help accelerate the implementation of new storage technologies such as FRESH. We examine current obstacles and finally we list recommendations for regulators moving forward.

4. Key strategies for creating a favorable regulatory and market framework

The key strategies identified in this study to help create a favorable regulatory and market framework for renewable energy storage in the EU can be summarized in the following bullet points:

- Recognize energy storage as a distinct and eligible asset class in electricity systems (not simply generation or consumption).
- Ensure fair grid access, transparent tariffs/charges and non-discriminatory treatment of storage.
- Enable storage to participate in multiple market services (e.g., energy arbitrage, flexibility, ancillary services, capacity) to stack revenues.
- Streamline permitting, infrastructure integration, standardization and sustainability of storage technologies.
- Harmonize rules across Member States to facilitate scalability and cross-border deployment.

4.1 Key Policy & Instruments currently implemented in the EU

According to the Joint Research Centre (JRC) “Policy and Regulatory Framework” overview, the EU has progressively recognized storage via the Clean Energy for All Europeans package (Electricity Directive (EU) 2019/944 and Electricity Regulation (EU) 2019/943).² These reforms support fair market access and grid integration rights for storage assets. National frameworks (for example in Cyprus) show that transmission/distribution rules and trading and settlement rules are being amended to allow storage facilities participation in electricity markets. One of the regulatory challenges is to ensure that storage is not over-charged from, for example double network charges. For example, national reforms can facilitate storage market participation and remove such discriminatory charges. Market design efforts include enabling storage to participate in wholesale markets, balancing/ancillary services and capacity mechanisms. Such participation supports “revenue-stacking” and business model viability.

Regarding infrastructure, the EU emphasizes timely permitting and infrastructure roll-out for storage integrated with renewables and grids that highlights storage as a key enabler of renewables and grid flexibility. Standardization and sustainability: e.g., forthcoming Battery Regulation, the requirement for circularity, supply-chain transparency, and lifecycle considerations for storage technologies (Table 1). The EU

supports storage through R&I programs such as Horizon Europe and through national/international funding schemes. Frameworks such as the Regulation on Horizon Europe (EU 2021/695) set the rules for participation and dissemination of research & innovation relevant for storage policy measures. The publications office of the EU Policy workshops and working groups (e.g., the BRIDGE “Regulation Working Group”) are analyzing regulatory barriers for storage, energy sharing, peer-to-peer trading and sector coupling.

Table 1: A summary of EU Policy Measures Relevant to Energy Storage

Date	Instrument or Legal Act	Summary of Key Provisions that are relevant to storage	Status
14/03/2023	Recommendation on Energy Storage – Underpinning a decarbonised and secure EU energy system (C(2023) 1729) Energy+2Publications Office of the EU+2	The Recommendation sets out concrete actions for Member States relating to energy storage: e.g. that storage should be recognized in market / network design; that network charges/ tariffs should reflect storage’s specific characteristics; that permitting and grid-integration should be streamlined; that revenue-stacking and long-term visibility are needed to attract investment. Energy+2Publications Office of the EU+2	Non-binding but influential. It provides a high-level policy orientation; Member States are encouraged to implement but legislation is not mandatory.
12/07/2023	Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 on Batteries and Waste Batteries (Batteries Regulation) European Chemicals Agency+2Circular Cities and Regions Initiative+2	While this regulation is not exclusively about energy storage, it has significant implications for storage technologies (especially battery-based). Key provisions include sustainability, safety and labelling requirements for batteries; minimum recycled content for industrial/EV/large batteries; chain-of-custody and due diligence obligations; product-passport/data requirements. EU BatteryRegulation+1	Entered into force 17/08/2023; further provisions phased in later. National implementation underway.
2024 (ongoing)	REPowerEU & associated guidance (Energy, Infrastructure, Flexibility) Energy	These initiatives emphasize rapid deployment of renewables & storage, diversification of energy supply, and flexibility in systems. While not a single legislative act just for storage, the framework drives the market environment: e.g., supporting storage co-location with renewables, grid flexibility services, infrastructure roll-out.	In force, national Recovery & Resilience Plans (RRPs) integrate related measures; supports funding and regulatory push.
2025 (expected/ongoing)	Guidance / future market-design reforms for storage, network tariffs & charges Energy+1	The EU is working on guidance and future reforms to ensure storage can participate in markets, access multiple services, and face non-discriminatory charges/tariffs. For example, network tariff design for storage is identified as key. Energy	These are at the guidance/reform stage; national transposition and design is still evolving.

Outside of the EU, programs such as the Energy Storage Grand Challenge (ESGC) have been adopted in the USA. Announced in January 2021, the Energy Storage Grand Challenge (ESGC) is a program at the US

Department of Energy (DoE) to develop and manufacture energy storage technologies. The initiative builds on the Energy Storage Grand Challenge Roadmap released in December 2020, which aims to reduce the levelized cost of long duration energy storage by 90 % down to \$0.05/kWh and the manufactured cost for a battery pack by 44 % to 80/kWh by 2030. Managed by the DoE, the ESGC redirects and expands competitive grants for energy storage R&D projects. Since 2020, the DoE has published 11 calls for proposals related to the ESGC.

4.2 Key challenges and shortcomings of existing frameworks that need to be addressed

This study has identified several shortcomings of existing EU regulations that must be addressed to favor the progression of storage technologies such as FRESH. There exists for example a certain amount of fragmentation across Member States. While there is EU-level direction, many national rules remain inconsistent (such as classification of storage, grid charges, market participation) which complicates pan-EU deployment. Regarding business models, ensuring storage can access multiple markets and services is not yet uniformly achieved across different jurisdictions. Grid integration & excessive charges exist. Avoiding double charges (e.g., for consumption and generation) and ensuring cost-reflective network tariffs remains a barrier. Another aspect is the systems for permits and delays in infrastructure. Storage co-located with renewables or grids still faces permitting inertia, grid-connection bottlenecks and the existence of unclear rules. Sustainability and supply chain issues remain, for example storage technologies (especially battery-based) face increasing pressure regarding raw materials, recyclability and environmental regulations, which increase costs and complexity. Standardization and interoperability are issues to be addressed. Without common standards across Europe for storage assets, pilots may struggle to scale or replicate. Market design for long-duration storage is critical as energy storage durations lengthen (e.g., >12 h, seasonal), regulatory frameworks still need to catch up (locational pricing, temporal flexibility markets). *FRESH technology targets long term energy storage at a seasonal level.*

5. Recommendations by the FRESH consortium for creating a favorable regulatory and market framework

Regulations designed to help and promote the renewable energy storage sector at the EU level are gaining traction. As described in Section 3.1, EU legislation, for example the Clean Energy for All Europeans package, is coming online. However, as outlined in Section 4.2, several challenges and shortcomings still exist that if addressed appropriately can accelerate the adoption of new storage technologies such as FRESH. The FRESH consortium has identified the following recommendations at a regulatory level. Given the policy/market context and project objectives, the following recommendations are pertinent. They are described in bullet form.

5.1 Seven Policy Recommendations: Strengthening EU Support for Energy Storage

To consolidate progress and fully realize the benefits of storage, the EU should pursue a mix of binding targets, market harmonization, and funding reforms as follows:

1. Establish Binding EU-Wide Storage Targets

The EU should set a binding 2030 or 2040 storage capacity targets—for example, 200 GW—to provide investor confidence and align national strategies with broader decarbonization objectives.

2. Harmonize Market Rules and Remove Remaining Barriers

The EU could issue dedicated Energy Storage Regulations or guidance under the ACER framework to standardize permitting, eliminate double grid charges, and ensure equal market access across member states.

3. Expand and Target EU Funding Instruments

Existing mechanisms such as the Innovation Fund, InvestEU, and the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) should be expanded to prioritize long-duration storage (e.g., hydrogen, thermal, compressed air) and cross-border flexibility projects.

4. Integrate Storage into Capacity and Flexibility Markets

The EU should require member states to include storage in capacity remuneration mechanisms and support the creation of EU-wide flexibility markets that reward rapid response and grid support services.

5. Strengthen Research, Innovation, and Industrial Strategy

Through Horizon Europe, the SET Plan, and the European Battery Alliance, the EU should foster R&D in next-generation storage technologies while promoting a resilient European supply chain under the Net-Zero Industry Act.

6. Link Storage with Hydrogen and Sector Coupling Policies

Integrating storage into the Hydrogen and Decarbonised Gas Market Package and REPowerEU would enhance multi-sector flexibility by supporting “Power-to-X” technologies that connect electricity, heat, and transport sectors.

7. Ensure Sustainability and Circularity

The EU should extend the principles of the Battery Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 to other storage technologies, ensuring environmental responsibility throughout the lifecycle from materials sourcing to end-of-life recycling.

5.2 Regional examples of good practice in the EU

An example of national based approach used by Germany that can be used as an example for other member countries. Germany has effectively implemented EU renewable energy storage regulations by integrating the Electricity Directive (EU) 2019/944 into national law through the Energiewirtschaftsgesetz (Energy Industry Act). This legal reform formally recognizes energy storage as an independent asset class, allowing storage operators to participate in balancing markets and ancillary services without being classified as traditional generators or consumers. To further promote the sector, the KfW Development Bank offers low-interest loans and grants for battery storage systems linked to solar PV installations across residential and commercial markets. Additionally, the Innovation Auctions Scheme under the Renewable Energy Sources Act (EEG 2023) incentivizes hybrid renewable and storage projects, emphasizing system flexibility over mere generation capacity. As a result of these regulatory and financial measures, Germany surpassed 8 GW of installed battery storage capacity by 2024, marking significant growth in both household and utility-scale deployments. Today, Germany’s grid services market is among the most advanced in Europe, setting a strong example for integrating storage into a flexible, renewable-based energy system. An example of a southern EU country,

Italy's energy regulator ARERA has implemented EU-compliant market reforms allowing storage systems to access multiple revenue streams, including energy arbitrage, frequency regulation, and congestion management. The Terna "Fast Reserve" auctions incentivize rapid-response storage technologies that enhance grid reliability. Italy's favorable regulatory environment has made it a key hub for large-scale battery investments in southern Europe.

6 Summary and conclusions

To further strengthen renewable energy storage deployment, the EU should set binding targets, harmonize market rules, expand funding, create stable flexibility markets, and integrate storage into its industrial and hydrogen strategies. This comprehensive approach would not only accelerate the energy transition but also position the EU as a global leader in clean energy flexibility and innovation. Energy storage has a fundamental role to play in the transition to an energy economy based on renewable energy. To facilitate the development of new storage technologies like FRESH, a coordinated package of policy measures is required. In this report we have identified seven recommendations for strengthening the energy storage sector in the EU.

References:

1. Determinants of Renewable Energy Development: Evidence from the EU Countries, *Energies* 2022, 15(19), 7093; <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15197093>
2. <https://ses.jrc.ec.europa.eu/storage-inventory>
3. *Engineering Science & Technology Journal* P-ISSN: 2708-8944, E-ISSN: 2708-8952 Volume 5, Issue 8, pp 2589-2615, August 2024 DOI: 10.51594/estj.v5i8.1460.
4. <https://www.rescoop.eu/> Enabling frameworks for Renewable Energy Communities Report on good practices
5. Anis Omri, Sami Ben Jabeur, *Climate policies and legislation for renewable energy transition: The roles of financial sector and political institutions*, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Volume 203, 2024, 123347, ISSN 0040-1625.
6. EU4Energy project. 20 RENEWABLE ENERGY Policy Recommendations 2018.
7. Key Enablers to Triple Renewables by 2030: Policy and Regulations 22 July 2024, International Renewable Energy Agency.
8. European Commission (2019). Directive (EU) 2019/944 on Common Rules for the Internal Market for Electricity.
9. European Commission (2019). Regulation (EU) 2019/943 on the Internal Market for Electricity.
10. European Commission (2023). Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 concerning Batteries and Waste Batteries.
11. European Commission (2022). REPowerEU Plan.
12. ACER (2023). *Energy Storage and Flexibility in the European Market*.
13. National Energy and Climate Plans (Germany, Spain, France, Italy, 2023–2024 editions).

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